

Entrepreneurship And Its Various Determinants

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Abstract

Purpose Entrepreneurship has become a widely disused and practiced topic across the globe. Its power to transform the societal pattern of working class into self employed individuals has gained the attention of policy makers and stakeholders at large. Thus, the focus of study is on ascertaining various determinants that influence the practice of entrepreneurship among individuals.

Design/methodology/approach this study has included the review of pertinent studies in the realm of entrepreneurship through a systematic analysis approach of (Paul & Criado 2020).

Findings the review indicates a significant amount of literature in the field of culture and religion affecting entrepreneurship additionally, research remains void in certain areas such as belief and ethnicity.

Research limitations/implications the review indicates that is a dearth of studies in Indian context together with few longitudinal studies have been undertaken so far thereby, creating a direction for future research projects.

Practical implications the findings of the study have important implications for those who formulate and implement policies regarding entrepreneurship.

Originality/value the study has tried to ascertain the possible determinant of entrepreneurship through a categorization of economic and non economic variables.

Keywords

Entrepreneurship, Economic, Non Economic, Innovation.

Introduction

In the present era of massive industrialization followed by a growth and transformation of the countries into industrial and manufacturing hubs. Entrepreneurship has positively affected the economies worldwide. The important contributing factor towards the changing scenario of development resorts to the practice of entrepreneurship. Countries have strikingly recognized the importance of entrepreneurship as an engine of economic growth and advancement. Entrepreneurship has successfully resulted in solving the problem of unemployment and poverty reduction. It has successfully transformed ideology of people from interest in the category of job seekers (working class) to self-employment. It is gradually turning the pace of development towards new avenues. The field of entrepreneurship has emerged as one of the most germane field of study seeking the attention of world leaders as a pertinent source of economic development.

The word Entrepreneur was first introduced by R. Cantillon (Robert et al., 1989) where he described entrepreneur as an individual who in the wake of uncertainty engages himself in a business activity for earning profit. Cantillon has focused more on the functions of entrepreneurs rather than the individual characteristics. Therefore he asserted generalized functions of people involved in entrepreneurship. Another prominent author Joseph Schumpeter recognized entrepreneurs as a pertinent figure in the economic growth of the nation. Entrepreneur is recognized as a person “who innovates and makes new combinations in production”. According to him entrepreneurship is a process of “creative destruction” carried out by entrepreneurs. Entrepreneur is an individual who in the wake of uncertainty tries to mitigate the risk through effective decision making in the utilization of resources directed towards the creation of innovative products or serve the existing market differently.

The role played by entrepreneur in the economic development of the nation is pertinent. He is the one responsible for channelizing the resources of the nation into new and innovative business opportunities leading to the creation of fruitful

results in employment generation and capital formation. Therefore, the presence of entrepreneurs in the economy is important and to understand the factors and variables that turn individuals into entrepreneurs is paramount for increasing the majority of entrepreneurs in the economy. By delving in the literature relating to entrepreneurship through this research we present the possible factors or determinants that are backing the creation of entrepreneurs as a behaviour and practice. For the purpose of this review, all the factors are grouped under economic and non-economic factors affecting entrepreneurship. The grouping not only result in ascertaining the most relevant factor contributing to the development of entrepreneurship but also help us indentifying the determinates where there is fewer attention resorted by authors and researchers therefore, efforts are made to include all the pertinent studies in the realm of entrepreneurship.

Objective of study

1. Analyze the concept of entrepreneurship.
2. Determine the various factors affecting entrepreneurship.
3. Grouping of the various factors underthe heads as economic and non-economic.
4. Suggesting future research directions.

Source: Adopted from Elali et al, 2016

Review of Literature

Determinants of Entrepreneurship

Although there are many factors that affect the growth of entrepreneurship but certain factors such as economic, social, cultural and personal dominate the pertinent literature. For the ease of understanding all these factors are grouped under two heads such as economic and non-economic factors. (Castaño et al., 2015) Economic factors such as a liberal monetary policy lead to the lowering of the interest rates, which magnifies the level of investment in the economy resulting in entrepreneurship. Similarly, it has been observed, that the levels of innovation positively contributes to the development of new business houses or the practice of entrepreneurship. Government policies (Amponsah et al., 2017) are basic terms and action by the government directed towards improving entrepreneurship. If the policies are suitable for startups, then there are higher chances that its growth will positively contribute towards the overall GDP of countries.

Personality traits such as confidence, attitude and self-esteem are the mostly wide and contributing factors towards the growth of entrepreneurship. Research in this realm has been extensive and shows the influence of these factors on the practice of entrepreneurship by entrepreneurs in different countries. Education on the other hand helps individuals in talking financial decisions and understands the policies that result in the selection of entrepreneurship as a career option. The culture and social network (Canedo et al., 2014) of individuals has a strong backing for entrepreneurship. For instance, the culture of borrowing money and acquisition of resources foster the growth and development of entrepreneurs who are risk takers. The social network of individuals sometimes motivates individuals

towards self-employment through the process of knowledge and resource sharing followed by financial and emotional support.

Therefore, there are good numbers of factors that affect the growth of entrepreneurship in different countries but the impact of such factors may vary depending on the social, geographical, political and economic scenarios in different countries. For a better understanding of the prevailing literature the factors are further classified into two groups such as economic and non-economic factors.

Main Text**Economic factors**

Entrepreneurship often sprouts from factor such as profits, financial gains and wealth maximization. Some authors have also categorized entrepreneurship in categories such as opportunity driven and necessity driven (Devece et al., 2016). The necessity driven entrepreneurship is dependent on economic factors therefore results for the motive of earning higher returns in order to satisfy economic needs of individuals. Another relevant economic factor is the availability of credit which allows entrepreneurs to pursue an innovative opportunity. For the facilitation of credit facilities the role played by financial institutions (Nguyen et al., 2019) is foremost important that ultimately finance the projects resulting in capital formation in countries. Entrepreneurship also results from the existence of demand in the market. An elevated demand for a product or service results in the increased attention of opportunity seekers referred as entrepreneurs. Another factor that helps in enhancing the level of entrepreneurship is economic growth. It has been observed in the studies that there are more entrepreneurs in developing countries rather than developed nations due to the presence of favorable demand and economic conditions that prevail in these economies together with the presence of unsatisfied demands in the country that results in the creation of new market. Some studies have also revealed that trade cycles significantly influence the growth and existence of entrepreneurs. The results highlights that there are relatively more number of entrepreneurs in the period of recession. As more entrepreneurs are born out of the existence of unemployment during the time frame of recession. Elevating prices is also an import factor contributing to the growth of entrepreneurs. The situation of rising prices motivates individuals towards higher returns and profitability therefore, results in the development of entrepreneurship activities.

Non-Economic factors

One of the success factors that lead to the generation of entrepreneurship is opportunity recognition. Opportunity recognition (Devece et al., 2016) gives impetus to the process of entrepreneurship paving a way towards the development of products and services that can be marketed. But the central point that has been discussed in the research is the support of economic factors that leads to the determination of favorable opportunity. Other non- economic factor is the presence of motivation to pursue the goals for entrepreneurship. The presence of determination and self- belief supports the process. Social network (Elali et al., 2016) plays an important role in the development of entrepreneurship ventures. Social network consist of family, friends, colleagues and relatives. With the backing of these groups individuals can practice networking leading creation of ventures. Another trait is the ability to recognize the opportunity that essentially segregate individuals from entrepreneurs. As the presence of favorable opportunities foster the growth of entrepreneurship ventures but the ability to exploit the opportunities (Rasli et al., 2013) depends on the factors other than economic. The development of technology is also fostering the process of entrepreneurship through the advent of latest advancement, individuals are able to think and produce differently. (Danish et al., 2019) Culture is one of the most widely accepted and discussed factors contributing toward the development of entrepreneurship. Culture encompasses religion, morality, ethics and behaviour towards outside environment. Other non-economic factors include essentially the personal characteristics of individuals that channelize their energy towards setting up of new ventures and become entrepreneurs. Factors such as risk bearing capacity have important implication towards setting up of a business unit. It has been observed in studies that individual who are willing to work in an environment of risk and uncertainty have significantly greater chances of becoming entrepreneurs. The Need of achievement is a pertinent factor that pushes individuals towards entrepreneurship. It explains the individual needs of attaining a position that is relatively better than the present state of entrepreneurs resulting in inner satisfaction of accomplishment. Other factor include such as self-efficacy that is the individual capabilities and competencies that enable them to practice entrepreneurship. Individuals with high level of self-efficacy consider themselves highly competitive and competent enough to find solutions for

complex business problems. Therefore, the presence of self-efficacy is significantly influence the process of entrepreneurship.

Conclusion

The study was targeted towards finding the factors that are pertinent to the growth of entrepreneurship practice. A thorough review of relevant literature suggests that there are numerous factors that influence the pace of entrepreneurship. Economic factors such as availability of finance, resources and economic factors considerably influence the decision of individuals towards become entrepreneurs. Non economic factors such as culture, personal, and social factors also has a bearing on the decision of becoming entrepreneurs. After the review of studies it has been found that in the earlier phases of entrepreneurship it was the economic factors that were at play. It is in the later years that the non-economic factors got recognition as an important factors contributing to the growth of entrepreneurship. It is also revealed that economic factors are so called the parts of external environment that asserts pressure on the individual pursuing entrepreneurship. The non economic factors are linked to the individual and are relatively internal affecting different individuals differently.

In the modern day, it is being observed there is greater number of studies researching the influence of non-economic factors than economic factors but after the review it has been asserted that both kinds of variables contribute significantly towards the growth of entrepreneurship. Therefore, for understanding entrepreneurship the study and knowledge of all these factors is essential so as to direct the future researches

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